

Electrical Characterization of electroluminescent Poly(vinylcarbazole) - Zinc Oxide nanoparticle composite devices

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Abstract: We demonstrate that Zinc Oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles into electroluminescent poly(vinylcarbazole) (PVK) polymer materials results in increased current densities, brightness, and luminance efficiencies in polymer light emitting devices (PLEDs). For low turn-on voltages, increase in current density, and good stability is achieved. At 9V, we achieve brightness of 743 cd/m² with luminance efficiencies 0.35 cd/A for PVK-ZnO nanocomposite devices. Electroluminescence (EL) spectra reveal that EL yield of PVK-ZnO nanoparticles devices increased greatly as compared with pure PVK devices

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of organic devices has been driven by a growing demand for low-cost and flexible electronics devices and information displays. Polymer light emitting diodes (PLEDs) using solution processes can be promising candidates for large area, fast-response, and flexible displays. Major important technological issues related to commercial applications are the quantum efficiency, device stability, and easy fabrication. However, the potential use of electroluminescence devices is ultimately limited by their low quantum efficiency as well as their poor stability. In spite of these critical drawbacks, the polymer light emitting device is still receiving considerable attention due to its several merits; they are easy fabrication with low cost, low operating voltage, flexibility, etc. One of the major reasons for the low quantum efficiency of single layer PLEDs is that the electron injection is more difficult than hole injection in most polymer light emitting devices due to high energy barrier to electron injection and low electron mobility in most conjugated polymers. Therefore, one of the most important challenges in the field of polymer LEDs is to better balanced charge carrier injection that is essential for high efficiency, Charge carrier mobility plays an important role in determining electro

luminance device performance, which is closely related the balance for injection and transport of holes and electrons [1-3].

2. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Polymer light-emitting devices based on ZnO nanoparticle doped with PVK polymer material have been technically prepared by the solution-based spin coating technique. Current density-voltage and Brightness-voltages characteristics demonstrated that the ZnO nanoparticle have the ability to improve the current density, and brightness, which may be caused by the enhancement of charge injection and charge transport. In addition, the ZnO nanoparticles appear to modify the device interfacial morphology, which facilitates electron injection. To improve both the EL lifetime and the luminance efficiency of a PLED simultaneously. The PVK/ZnO nanoparticle composite devices have current efficiencies higher than that of the pristine PVK devices.

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